

(2833) Proposal to conserve the name *Phalacroma* (Dinophysales: Dinophyceae)**Fernando Gómez**

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- (2833) *Phalacroma* F. Stein, Organism. Infusionsthier 3(2): 9, 23, 24. Nov 1883, nom. cons. prop.
 Typus: *P. porodictyum* F. Stein

Stein (Organism. Infusionsthier 3(2): 9, 23, 24. 1883) described the dinophysoid genus *Phalacroma* as distinct from *Dinophysis* Ehrenb. (in Ber. Bekanntm. Verh. Königl. Preuss. Akad. Wiss. Berlin 1839: 157. 1839). Balech (in Physis 19: 429. 1944) noted that *Phalacroma* F. Stein was a later homonym of the trilobite *Phalacroma* Hawle & Corda (in Abh. Königl. Böhm. Ges. Wiss., ser. 5, 5: 159. 1847). In consequence, he proposed the replacement name *Prodinophysis* Balech, and transferred to it 41 species of *Phalacroma*. In this he was followed by Loeblich (in Taxon 14: 16. 1965; 16: 68. 1967), who transferred another 25 species of *Phalacroma* into *Prodinophysis*.

Stein (l.c.) treated the dinoflagellates as animalcules (“Infusionsthier”) and proposed *Phalacroma* under the provisions of zoological nomenclature. The zoological name *Phalacroma* Hawle & Corda (l.c.) has been used after 1899, and so the provision for reversal of precedence under Art. 23.9.1 of the *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature* (Ride & al., Int. Code Zool. Nomencl., ed. 4: 28. 1999) does not apply. Under the *ICZN*, *Phalacroma* F. Stein is “objectively invalid”, equivalent to illegitimate under the *ICN*, because only a senior homonym may be used as a “valid name” (i.e., as a correct name) (Art. 52.2 of the *ICZN*). *Phalacroma* F. Stein satisfies the provisions for “publication” of the *ICZN* and thus for valid publication under Art. 45.1 of the *ICN* (although *Phalacroma* would, in any case be validly published under the *ICN* without that provision).

The status under the *ICN* of a name such as *Phalacroma* was amended at the Shenzhen Congress such that Art. 54.1 of the *ICN* now states in part, “Consideration of homonymy does not extend to the names of taxa not treated under this *Code*, except as stated below [...]. (b) A name applied to an organism covered by this *Code* and validly published under it (Art. 32–45) but originally published for a taxon other than an alga, fungus, or plant, i.e. under another *Code*, is illegitimate if it (1) is unavailable for use under the provisions of the other *Code*, usually because of homonymy, [...]”. Consequently, *Phalacroma* F. Stein, being unavailable for use (“objectively invalid”) under the *ICZN*, is illegitimate under the *ICN*, and the substitute name *Prodinophysis* would be the correct name for this dinoflagellate genus if no other earlier name applied to it.

Abé (in Publ. Seto Mar. Biol. Lab. 15: 38–77. 1967) and Balech (in Revista Mus. Argent. Ci. Nat., Bernardino Rivadavia Inst. Nac.

Invest. Ci. Nat., Hidrobiol. 2: 79–92. 1967) carried out studies on dinophysoid dinoflagellates, and they concluded that *Phalacroma* should be treated as a junior synonym of *Dinophysis*. Consequently Abé (l.c.) and Balech (l.c. 1967: 82–85) transferred the species of *Phalacroma* into *Dinophysis*. As a result, the name *Phalacroma* was not used by most authors for the next 40 years, and the substitute name *Prodinophysis* Balech was forgotten for more than 50 years (except by Böhm in Biblioth. Phycol. 22: 104, 110, 112, 114. 1976). The synonymy of numerous taxa has been tested with the advent of molecular data. Jensen & Daugbjerg (in J. Phycol. 45: 1136–1152. 2009) revealed that the DNA sequence of material of *P. porodictyum* F. Stein (l.c.: legend to t. 18, fig. 11–14), the species that provides the type of *Phalacroma*, was distantly related to the sequence of material of the species that provides the type of *Dinophysis*, *D. acuta* Ehrenb. (l.c.). This supported the treatment of *Phalacroma* and *Dinophysis* as independent genera. Jensen & Daugbjerg (l.c. 1147) emended the description of *Phalacroma* and proposed a lectotype (Stein, l.c.: t. 18, fig. 11) and epitype (Jensen & Daugbjerg, l.c.: 1141, fig. 3N) for *P. porodictyum*. These authors did not mention *Prodinophysis* as a synonym of *Phalacroma*, or make any comment on the homonymy. Both *Phalacroma* F. Stein and *Prodinophysis* Balech are currently listed as distinct genera in Algaebase: https://www.algaebase.org/search/genus/detail/?genus_id=44962 and https://www.algaebase.org/search/genus/detail/?genus_id=46078 on the basis of a statement in ING (<https://naturalhistory2.si.edu/botany/ing/>) “*Prodinophysis* is correct in zoological nomenclature because of *Phalacroma* Hawle et Corda 1847 (Trilobita)”. However, this entry in ING must predate the *Shenzhen Code* (Turland & al. in Regnum Veg. 159. 2018) because, under its Art. 54.1(b)(1), *Phalacroma* F. Stein is an illegitimate name and *Prodinophysis* is a legitimate name for the genus under both Codes.

The generic name *Prodinophysis* has not been used in the dinoflagellate literature for the last 40 years, while *Phalacroma* is currently in common use. Since the reinstatement of *Phalacroma* (Jensen & Daugbjerg, l.c.), three new species have been proposed (Parra-Toriz & al. in Nova Hedwigia 99: 85–86. 2014; Esqueda-Lara & Hernández-Becerril in Nova Hedwigia 105: 301–312. 2017).

Prodinophysis Balech is only the correct name for the species placed in *Phalacroma* in the absence of any earlier name being considered a synonym of the latter. However, other earlier generic names have either been referred to *Phalacroma* at one time or may well be applicable to it. These are *Pseudophalacroma* Jørg. (in Schmidt, Rep. Danish Oceanogr. Exped. 1908–10, ser. 2, 2: 3, 47. 1923) with original type *P. nasutum* (F. Stein) Jørg. (l.c.: 4. 1923; = *Phalacroma nasutum*

F. Stein, l.c.: t. 18. fig. 1–8 = *Prodinophysis nasuta* (F. Stein) Loeb. 1965 = *Dinophysis nasuta* (F. Stein) Parke & P.S. Dixon 1968); *Oxyphysis* Kof. (in Univ. Calif. Publ. Zool. 28: 205. 1926) with original type *O. oxytoxoides* Kof. (= *Phalacroma oxytoxoides* (Kof.) F. Gómez & al. in J. Phycol. 47: 404. 2011); and *Dinofurcula* Kof. & Skogsb. (in Mem. Mus. Comp. Zool. Harvard Coll. 51: 201. 1928) with original type *D. ultima* (Kof.) Kof. & Skogsb. (= *Phalacroma ultima* Kof. in Bull. Mus. Comp. Zool. 50: 195. 1907). [Loeblich & Loeblich (in Stud. Trop. Oceanogr. 3: 52. 1966) considered *Pseudophalacroma* Jørg. not to be a validly published name being “provisionally established”. However, Jørgensen clearly accepted *Pseudophalacroma* providing a Latin diagnosis (l.c.: 47) and publishing the new combination *P. nasutum* (l.c.: 4), thus satisfying the requirements of Art. 36.1 of the ICN for valid publication.]

Other morphologically related genera to *Phalacroma* are *Metaphalacroma* L.S. Tai & Skogsb. (in Arch. Protistenk. 82: 457. 1934) with original type *M. skogsbergii* L.S. Tai (in Tai & Skogsb. l.c.), *Proheteroschisma* L.S. Tai & Skogsb. (l.c.: 460) with original type *P. connectens* L.S. Tai & Skogsb., and *Latifascia* Loeb. & A.R. Loeb. (l.c.: 38) (= *Heteroschisma* Kof. & Skogsb., l.c.: 36, nom. rej.) with original type *L. inaequale* (Kof. & Skogsb.) Loeb. & A.R. Loeb. (l.c.: 38). Molecular data that might confirm the relationship with *Phalacroma* are lacking for *Dinofurcula*, *Latifascia* and *Proheteroschisma*. Molecular data are available for *Metaphalacroma*, *Pseudophalacroma*, and *Oxyphysis*. Gómez & al. (in J. Eukaryot. Microbiol. 59: 189. 2012) demonstrated that the small subunit ribosomal RNA gene sequence of the type of *Pseudophalacroma* is only distantly related to that of the type of *Phalacroma*, supporting the generic recognition of *Pseudophalacroma*. Gómez & al. (l.c. 2012: 189) also reported the DNA sequence of an individual identified as *Metaphalacroma* sp. (likely *M. skogsbergii*); this and unpublished data (GenBank No. FJ561749 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/238683611>) suggest a distant relationship to the sequence of *P. porodictyum*, the type of *Phalacroma*. There is, therefore, no support to consider either *Pseudophalacroma* or *Metaphalacroma* as synonymous with *Phalacroma*.

By contrast, Gómez & al. (l.c. 2011: 403–404) demonstrated that the DNA sequence of *O. oxytoxoides*, the type of *Oxyphysis*, is very closely related to that of the type of *Phalacroma*, *P. porodictyum*, and consequently treated *Oxyphysis* as a synonym of *Phalacroma*,

proposing the new combination *Phalacroma oxytoxoides* (Kof.) F. Gómez & al. However, Hoppenrath & al. (in Lewis & al., Biol. Geol. Perspect. Dinoflagellates: 199–206. 2013) questioned the synonymy of *Oxyphysis* and *Phalacroma*. Hoppenrath & al. (l.c.: 205), while endorsing the close relationship of *Oxyphysis* with *Phalacroma* and considering that the monotypic family *Oxyphysaceae* Sournia (in Phycologia 23: 350. 1984) was no longer warranted, nevertheless considered that the “transfer of *Oxyphysis* into the genus *Phalacroma* [...] was premature”, going on to state that “significant morphological differences exist between *Oxyphysis* and *Phalacroma*”. However, if the synonymy of *Phalacroma* and *Oxyphysis* is accepted, the latter is the earliest available name for the group of congeneric species currently placed in *Phalacroma*, nom. illeg. Excluding species of *Phalacroma* that do not cluster in the clade of the type, a total of 84 new combinations of *Oxyphysis* would need to be proposed if *Phalacroma* is not conserved. A conserved name is made legitimate despite being previously illegitimate (Art. 14.1) and so the conservation of *Phalacroma* overcomes its illegitimacy under Art. 54.1 and serves stability of nomenclature (Art. 14.2) by maintaining the widely used name and avoiding all these new combinations. On the other hand, rejection of this proposal is coherent with other cases of names of dinoflagellate genera that are junior homonyms of zoological names (proposals Nos. 477, *Abedinium* against *Leptophyllus*; 493, *Dogelodinium* against *Collinella*; 497, *Gyrodinium* against *Spirodinium*; 502, *Keppenodinium* against *Hollandella*; 503, *Latifascia* against *Heteroschisma*; 513, *Sphaeripara* against *Lohmannia* – Wiersma & al., Shenzhen Code, App. I–VII. 2018–, <https://naturalhistory2.si.edu/botany/codes-proposals/> [accessed 19 Jul 2021]), and avoids having two distinct organisms with the same correct name (e.g., a bibliographical search on *Phalacroma* provides entries on trilobites and on the dinoflagellate).

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